

I.FAST

Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology
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I.FAST Knowledge Transfer Report: Assessment of Innovation Potential and KT Opportunities in IFAST R&D Activities

[WP3]

ABSTRACT

This I.FAST Knowledge Transfer Report contains the outcome of a survey carried out in the second half of 2021, as a combined effort of the I.FAST Tasks 3.1: “Coordination and industrial partnership support” and Task 3.2: “Knowledge Transfer and Business Opportunities in Accelerator R&D”. The survey was aimed at assessing the innovation potential and the technology transfer opportunities of the I.FAST R&D activities.

The KT report covers the general methodology and survey background, as well as the goals of the analysis and briefly discusses possible and planned next steps to be executed in the framework of the Task 3.2. This report represents the completion of the I.FAST milestone MS09.

I.FAST Consortium, 2022

For more information on I.FAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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1 Introduction & Acknowledgements

1.1 INTRODUCTION

In the context of the broader engagement and support of industry in I.FAST activities pursued by WP3: “Industry Engagement”, one of the main tasks is represented by the setup of a survey plan for assessing the innovation outcome of R&D activities involved in the project and the potential of these innovations to be implemented by industry, as well as a dedicated initial knowledge and technology transfer survey on the R&D activities.

This assessment was carried out together within the Task 3.1: “Coordination and industrial partnership support” and Task 3.2: “Knowledge Transfer and Business Opportunities in Accelerator R&D” and covers the initial expectations of the participants and can later on be compared with actual achievements obtained throughout the project.

This document aims at providing an interpretation of the initial expectations of I.FAST participants concerning the potential of the project R&D activities to produce innovations, in terms of new products, processes or services, that can be exploited both inside and outside the set of current participants.

To gauge the sentiment of the participants, we gathered their feedbacks through a questionnaire that was sent to all the leaders whose tasks involved R&D activities to be carried out with industry as well as those that are possibly of industrial relevance.

The objectives of this survey were:

- make a general assessment of the innovation and knowledge transfer potential associated with R&D activities in I.FAST;
- identify whether there may be risks or opportunities in the development and realization of this potential;
- evaluate if the level of industrial engagement in I.FAST is adequate or could be enhanced in some cases;
- verify if there are practical aspects that may limit the exploitation of the intellectual property produced in I.FAST.

1.2 BACKGROUND OF THIS REPORT

The I.FAST project aims at promoting exploitable results in combination with fostering the knowledge and technology transfer from within the various R&D activities to industry, both inside

and outside the set of current participants. This way, we try to stimulate the build-up of added industrial value, for instance in terms of creating new IP or protecting those already created, and building awareness of such topics within the research groups. This enables making results from the I.FAST R&D activities available to interested parties within and beyond the I.FAST Consortium, while protecting the legitimate interests of all I.FAST beneficiaries that have been involved in producing these results. One goal within the work package task 3.2 is to support the beneficiaries and activities in achieving an optimal exploitation of the knowledge transfer originated by I.FAST, such that in a broader scope we can enable the establishment of new and additional activities for existing companies as well as facilitate the creation of spin-offs from within the research institutions. This will be a process that will go well beyond the duration of the project.

All this holds in particular for those results that have a significant potential for commercial applications. The assessment of such potentials is a challenging task, as it involves not only considering protective measures while at the same time establishing a culture of trust and collaboration, but it also includes the evaluation of additional application areas and market assessments as well as in many cases strong and meaningful involvements of industrial partners. This knowledge transfer report will not only give a summary of the outcome of the initial analysis carried out within the first months of I.FAST, strongly relying on the provided information and opinions from the project leaders, but also present concrete starting points and leverage points for increasing and strengthening the knowledge transfer within I.FAST and beyond.

We highlight these as well as suggested further actions and the I.FAST knowledge transfer objectives. Nevertheless, it is important to note that this initial analysis and survey only presents a starting point in the investigations themselves, as we are only summarizing the current status and knowledge transfer plans, as a prerequisite to taking action for fostering knowledge transfer and optimizing knowledge transfer and exploitation, leading up to a dedicated business development case report for a specific I.FAST R&D sector in collaboration with industry.

1.3 GOAL OF THE ANALYSIS

In order to achieve above goals and to collaborate with the other work packages to enhance the areas with higher prospects of industrial impact and to be able to use, for this purpose, the available tools and opportunities, an initial survey and analysis on the planned and potential knowledge transfer with all its facets has been conducted. What we have tried to assess is the industrial innovation outcome and knowledge transfer potential and expectation of I.FAST R&D activities in general, at this stage focused on the initial status, based on the activities' own assessment and additional analysis. Evaluating the innovation potential, the possible obstacles and facilitating factors as the R&D activities themselves see them, is crucial for identifying also possible risks or opportunities in the development and realization of this potential. This will also support verifying if there are practical aspects that may limit the exploitation of the intellectual property produced in I.FAST.

How much the present innovation and knowledge transfer potential can actually be translated to meaningful outcomes is also strongly related to the level of industrial engagement. We have tried to assess whether the level of industrial engagement is adequate or could be enhanced in certain activities. Such an enhancement could be suitable both in the extent of participation of current industrial partners, or in bringing additional industry in, which might have certain specialized and yet lacking expertise they can bring in to support the development process. In those cases, where such an extended engagement is deemed useful, in a later step concrete measures to support this might be derived from the results.

Of course, not all activities are to be treated in the same way. Similar to how the potential of certain R&D activities might be larger than that of others, the current maturity level and its increase throughout the project has a significant influence on the possible innovation and knowledge transfer outcome and therefore also is part of this analysis. Here, both the current and potential technology readiness level at the end of I.FAST are valuable indicators on the status of the activity's development. A detailed analysis of I.FAST activities with high technology readiness levels and/or industry involvement therefore is part of the work package 3, as well as the identification of activities relevant within the field of industrial involvement, that currently have a relatively low technology readiness level and/or are without any industry involvement.

This will serve as a starting point for the ongoing discussion with I.FAST activities. In case of low TRL activities, the assessment of what can be done to support industry involvement or to add actions for additional value for industry is necessary for optimization of the transfer outcome. Likewise, one can already at an early-stage support how industrial partners can be attracted, where no explicit involvement is planned yet. For high TRL activities it is to be clarified what knowledge and

technology transfer activities are planned within the activities and what can be done to support and enhance these.

At the end of the following summary of the initial analysis, certain initial suggestions for measures to achieve these goals are provided, setting the fundament for the ongoing assessment and improvement of the innovation and knowledge transfer outcome of the I.FAST R&D activities.

1.4 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to thank the administrative personnel of INFN Padua/Elena Pavan from INFN Padua for her contributions in the set-up of the survey through the application Limesurvey.

2 Methodology

2.1 GENERAL METHODOLOGY AND SELECTION OF RELEVANT ACTIVITIES

The role of this survey plan is to assess the industrial innovation outcome and knowledge transfer potential/expectation of IFAST R&D activities in general, both in terms of initial expectations and of actual achievements based on the activities own assessment and additional analysis.

Therefore, we had to define the criteria to identify which out of a total of 54 Tasks we should consider relevant in terms of industrial innovation and knowledge transfer potential. To this end, we started analyzing IFAST's official documentation, namely the Grant Agreement and the Project Proposal, looking at the descriptions of the WPs and relative Tasks contained in these documents.

After this analysis based on prior information, we defined as relevant both those tasks which envisaged R&D activities to be carried out with industry and with industrial partners already defined, and activities with good chances of producing knowledge transfer but without any industrial partner in IFAST. This phase led us to skim the total number of tasks from 54 to 29. The following phase enabled us to check if each of the 29 Tasks identified were effectively relevant for the scope of the survey. Indeed, some Tasks consist of multiple relevant activities with rather different aspects of potential industrial innovation and possible technology transfer exploitation. In these cases, we asked the Task Leaders to forward the survey to those colleagues responsible for the individual R&D activities within the task they are responsible for to collect their feedbacks.

As last step, with the help of Mauro Morandin, WP3 Leader, we individually contacted the resulting Task Leaders to verify if their activities were effectively envisaging industrial involvement and had the ability to produce commercial results or knowledge transfers that can lead to industrial innovations. At the end of the process, we identified a set of 28 activities specifically interesting for the scope of the survey. The list of these task is shown in Section 5.3 in the Appendix. Eventually, as a result of our analysis, the "Innovation & KT" survey was sent per email to each of the 28 relevant tasks on July 27, 2021. By the end of September 2021, 17 coordinators had replied to our survey, resulting in a response rate of 61%.

2.2 QUESTIONS AND STRUCTURE OF THE SURVEY

The Survey is conceptually divided into two main sections, the first dedicated to those questions that aim to gauge the expectations for industrial innovation of the project activities and the level of industrial involvement thereof, the second is geared towards the assessment of the knowledge transfer

expectations and the potential commercial applications of these innovations. Based on these two main sections, representing the two different general topics of interest, the analysis and report itself is sorted to four parts, each with an emphasis on a different aspect of the topics of interest, and the results and analysis are likewise split into these four parts:

1. Questions concerning the potential of industrial innovation.
2. Questions on the industrial participation and involvement.
3. Questions about technology transfer expectations.
4. Questions about applications and commercialization.

As for the composition of the sections of the survey, they were made up of a variety of questions, mainly multiple choice but also with some free text replies. In particular, the whole survey consisted of a total of 35 aspects, of which 20 were addressed in a multiple-choice manner and the remaining 15 allowed for free text replies. The flowcharts in Section 5.20 of the appendix depict the structure of the survey and the relationships between the questions.

2.3 GENERAL OVERVIEW ON THE RESPONSES

After a careful analysis aimed at identifying the IFAST tasks that involve R&D activities to be conducted with industry and those suitable for Knowledge Transfer, we found out that 28 over a total of 54 tasks met this criterion, resulting in a coverage of 52% of the project activities.

The detailed list of the relevant task is shown in Table 1, while the coverage of total tasks achieved in absolute terms is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Distribution of covered tasks, how many have been contacted, and how many of those have replied to the questionnaire.

A total of 28 questionnaires have been distributed per email, one for each leader of the relevant activities identified. Out of this number, 17 tasks replied to our survey, resulting in a response rate of 61%. Figure 2 shows the questionnaires that have been sent and the replies we received both in absolute and relative terms.

Figure 2: The received replies in absolute and relative values.

3 Results of the Survey and Analysis

3.1 PART 1: QUESTIONS CONCERNING THE POTENTIAL OF INDUSTRIAL INNOVATION OF I.FAST ACTIVITIES

The questions of this section aim at gauging the expectations of the Task Leaders interviewed concerning the potential of their activities to generate industrial innovations/applications. Furthermore, considering that most of the R&D activities with potential industrial application stand at different starting TRL levels and that the project seeks to bring them closer to the market validation phase, this section also sets the stage for the following questions related to the potential for technology transfer activities connected with the declared innovation expectations.

3.1.1 What kind of innovation is it expected to be generated by the R&D activity?

Figure 3: Expected innovation that is generated by the R&D activity with three selectable options ranging from limited to significant innovation spill-over and industrial innovation.

This was the opening question of the survey whereby we wanted to understand the expectations of tasks leaders regarding the extent to which the activities under their control could generate industrial innovation.

The results are encouraging as 76% of the respondents claimed that the R&D activities they are carrying out, in itself or aided by a broader industrial involvement and/or knowledge transfer, can bring significant innovation to industrial products or processes.

Going into further details, the relative majority of respondents (41%) declared that their R&D efforts have already a clear and planned path that leads to industrial applications, while 35% of them claimed that their activities are targeting primarily applications for science, but knowledge transfer activities will make it possible to bring innovation to industrial products, processes or services. Only 24% of the interviewed expects a limited innovation spill-over to industrial partners by the end of IFAST, as the project activities of their tasks involve industry mainly in the supply of off-the-shelf or build-to-print components. In absolute terms, over a total of 17 replies, 4 went to Option 1, 6 to Option 2 and 7 to Option 3.

It is interesting to compare the answers given to this question to those given by the same people to questions concerning the expected TRL of the activities at the beginning and end of the project. Indeed, in principle we expect that tasks who choose Option 2 or 3 should claim that at the end of the project the activities they are working on should reach a high TRL (close to 7).

This comparison is carried out in Part 3 of this document, where enquiries related to TRL are analysed.

The following questions were made conditional upon the answer given to the previous one. If option 2 or 3 were chosen, a series of questions aimed at understanding what kind of improved products or processes were expected, which factors could facilitate, and which could obstacle the industrial innovation, were asked. The results of these 3 questions are analysed in paragraphs 2.2.2, 2.2.3 and 2.2.4 that follow.

Instead, whether option 1 one was chosen, we asked Task Leaders if they believed there were chances to strengthen the limited innovation spill-over they attributed to their activities. Results are encouraging as, 3 over 4 respondents (Option 1 was selected by 4 people in total) believe that improving the chances of generating innovative outcomes from their activities is possible.

Figure 4: Is there any possibility to strengthen this limited innovation spill-over?

We delved deeper into the matter with people who replied positively and asked them which were the opportunities of improvement they saw. Two of them claimed that stronger networking with other accelerator-based facilities and involvement of industrial partners can result in the development of devices that are compatible with many accelerator facilities and not only for the ones they were originally conceived. This leads us to think that it can be useful to increase the opportunities of exchange between different accelerator facilities and also with industry, which can contribute with its capabilities of standardization to make the innovation applicable across research infrastructures.

3.1.2 What kind of new or improved products, processes or services are expected to be eventually generated from the R&D activity?

The answers we received to this question were very specific of each task interviewed. In fact, as one can see from the list of the relevant tasks displayed in Table 1, each of them is characterized by a different focal topic and, consequently, a specific set of R&D activities.

Here several applications were mentioned, spanning fields such as environmental protection, electrical engineering, security (control at borders), material sciences (industrial radiography), medical technologies, accelerator technologies and components. As anticipated in the opening question, some of these innovations have a clear path towards commercialization, others instead have direct applications in science that can be extended to the broader market through knowledge transfer activities.

One example of a technology developed in the accelerators field with a clear path towards environmental application is pursued by Task 12.2, which will undertake the development of a prototype plant for treatment of municipal sewage sludge using an electron beam, with the aim of improving biogas production and the creation of high-value organic fertiliser from the waste. In this case, the scope of biohazards treatment and biomass valorisation is clear as the design of an advanced electron accelerator plant for biohazards treatment is the direct focus of the activity.

As for activities with applications in science but additional potential for industrial exploitation, they may be well represented by the development of pulsed superconducting magnets developed in WP8. These accelerator components are designed to bring the advantages of superconductivity making possible smaller and less expensive accelerator design. These advantages might also be brought to ion therapy, bringing cost advantages in the realization of accelerators for this kind of cancer treatment instruments based on accelerators.

3.1.3 Do you see any factors that may represent obstacles towards the effective exploitation of the innovation potential by industry?

Figure 5: Obstacles to overcome for effective exploitation as identified by the activities.

Despite the good prospects emerged from the opening question, the Task Leaders interviewed also acknowledged that there are some factors that may hold back the effective exploitation of the innovations by industry. The most cited obstacle was the manufacturing costs that firms might incur

to bring these innovations to the market. In fact, when it comes to innovative products, processes or services, the costs to produce and bring them to a certain scale should be carefully evaluated but it is difficult to estimate them ex-ante. According to the respondents, other aspects that may hinder the exploitation are the technical complexity that industry can face to transform a prototype into a reliable product, the uncertain business potential of a new solution or technology.

3.1.4 What are the opportunities to improve the chance or the extent of this exploitation?

Figure 6: What are the opportunities to improve the chance or the extent of this exploitation?

We also asked Task Leaders if they saw opportunities to further improve the exploitation potential of the innovations. As evidenced by other surveys distributed within previous EC financed projects on accelerators R&D, like Amici or Aries, the majority of respondents claimed that an earlier engagement of industrial companies in the process would be beneficial. In fact, when it comes to R&D projects led by RIs, most of the times companies are involved only in the last part of the development process as manufacturers of what has already been studied and designed by research institutions. This approach can cause issues during the production phase as RIs may not have the

same experience of industry concerning the criticalities of certain manufacturing processes where the right conceptualization during the design phase can play a crucial role.

Another important opportunity of improvement comes from the ability to reduce the implementation costs of the innovations. Here, the cost reduction stems from applying value engineering to accelerator components, from scaling-up their production through increased standardization across different machines or by conceiving the new technologies so that they can be applicable to different accelerator complexes. Finally, the interviewed cited also the importance of getting increased interest from industrial players by simplifying the production process of the components and by trying to give a clearer picture of the potential market value that the innovations can have for companies.

3.2 PART 2: QUESTIONS ON THE INDUSTRIAL PARTICIPATION AND INVOLVEMENT IN I.FAST ACTIVITIES

The innovation potential can in many cases one be fulfilled with a strong and meaningful involvement of involved industrial partners, for instance in terms of support within a common development. Therefore, for this report and the initial assessment of the activities it is crucial to highlight in which ways the various industrial partners are participating, how they are involved, how they are distributed and where there might be leverage for improving impact by stronger or more involvement. Questions and results aimed at clearing this aspect of the survey are summarized in the following.

3.2.1 How many companies are currently collaborating in the I.FAST activity?

Figure 7: Distribution of the number of companies involved in the activities based on the answers of the questionnaire.

It can be seen that the number of companies currently involved is spread well across the activities. Most activities that have answered our call (7) have currently only one industrial partner as part of the research group. In summary, in 12 % of the surveyed tasks there currently is no industrial

collaboration at all, while 47 % count more than one partner within their activity (from 2 to more than 3 industrial partners per task). In particular, 23% of the interviewed tasks reported having 2 companies, 12% having 3 and 12% more than 3.

3.2.2 How much do the activities think that enlarging the set of companies currently engaged could benefit their R&D activity?

Figure 8: This figure shows how large the participants of the survey assume the impact of having a larger number of involved companies on the R&D would be.

Only two answers stated not having any company involved in the activity. Of those, one is planning to take some actions to explore the possibility of an industrial involvement in the R&D activity both through exhibitions during conferences and through personal contacts. For both actions, no additional help is required, as contact with a dedicated technology transfer unit is already established. The activity not planning to take up actions to explore the possibility of an industrial involvement in the R&D activity does not see any benefit in terms of better commercialization/exploitation.

It was not only asked whether help with search of additional companies would be beneficial, which was not requested for now, but also what kind of companies would be suitable, and what they should bring with them. Mainly, it was stated that further involvement of the current set of companies would be of interest, rather than bringing in others, thus the only benefit adding additional industry partners

was noted in sharing risks. It was also noted, that in that case medium size companies “with collaborative” spirit would be desired.

3.2.3 How much can the activities benefit by stronger involvement of the companies currently engaged?

Figure 9: How much can your activities benefit by stronger involvement of the companies currently engaged?

In addition to asking for the suspected gain in bringing in further industry partners to the activities, we assessed the activities opinion on having a more extensive or stronger industrial involvement within the project.

Half of all respondents believe that greater involvement would have a very positive impact on developments in the task ("A lot"), while nearly all others at least do not deny such positive influence. Especially those activities with more than one industrial partner already have stated seeing such benefit, while most tasks with only one industry partner would not see the benefit similarly strong ("Not so much"). This could indeed hint at the overall industry relevance of the considered task, indicating that where more industry is involved a stronger involvement is likewise welcome. In total, also including the previous results, it can be understood, that an improve in the innovation outcome within the I.FAST project does not so much require more industry partners in many cases, but rather a more extensive participation of industry in general.

Figure 10: Number of activities that state having a benefit of stronger industrial involvement of the currently involved companies, separated by the number of companies currently involved in the considered R&D activity.

Figure 11: What form of additional industrial involvement of the companies currently engaged would be beneficial?

Within the group of tasks considering stronger industrial involvement as helpful, it was examined which type of involvement is deemed most beneficial. Here, all but one mentioned prototyping to be

most helpful. As prototyping is a significant step towards validation and commercialization, this is not surprising and indeed confirmed by the information provided prior to the survey, where prototyping was the most often stated requirement in further R&D for strengthening the outcome of exploitable results.

Additionally, both the access to expertise from industry and their support with component development were noted as valuable as additional involvement.

3.3 PART 3: QUESTIONS ABOUT TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER EXPECTATIONS

The exploitation of the fore- and background of the tasks within I.FAST depends on several aspects. The following questions are important to assess the value and potential of the work in terms of exploitation as well as possible challenges.

3.3.1 Technology Readiness Level of the activities now and at the end of I.FAST

Figure 12 shows the technology readiness level of all responding activities, both at the time of survey (“current level”), as well as they forecast for the end of the project (“Level at the end of I.FAST”). The TRL scale and definition is chosen from the standard definition of the European Union.

It can be seen that the initial levels are spread from TRL 1 (basic principles observed) up to TRL 4 (technology validated in lab). This is as expected within the scope of I.FAST. The TRL-estimation was also part of the proposal, Figure 14 presents the statistics based on this. Comparing both Figure 12 and Figure 14, it can be seen that the answers of the survey do not contradict the initial estimation and the spread across activities adequately covers the range of relevant activities.

The technology readiness trajectories from the questionnaire depicted here present a significant shift from activities currently mainly focused on fundamental research and experimental / laboratory level validation towards prototyping and system demonstration phases. The bulk of projects aims for a technology readiness level of 5 or higher, which is already considering the validation in a relevant environment.

What might seem surprising is the difference in the projected TRL. The answers of the survey lie in between 4 and 7, with most answers at the outer limits 4 and 7 and none at TRL 6. In contrast, the picture is different looking at the prior document, with most activities planning to reach TRL 6, one reaching 8 (starting at TRL 2) and two even staying within the concept formulation phase (TRL 2) even at the end of I.FAST. Some differences can be explained by the different set of tasks considered (i.e., not all tasks have responded). Apart from that, another explanation can be found in the perceived ambiguity between two neighboring levels or difficulty in determining the degree of maturity exactly to one level or another over such a long period of time.

Figure 12: Comparison of the technology readiness level of all responding activities at the time of survey (denoted with “current level”) versus the level they forecast for the end of the project (“Level at the end of I.FAST”).

Figure 13: Technology readiness level trajectories, connecting the TRL - as stated in the survey - at the beginning and end of I.F.A.S.T.

Figure 14: Comparison of the technology readiness level of all responding activities as stated in the proposal document (denoted with “current level”) versus the level they then have forecast for the end of the project (“Level at the end of I.F.A.S.T”).

On average, the responding activities plan to increase the technology readiness by 2.75 levels within the time frame of the I.F.A.S.T. project. It can also be seen, while most activities, especially at the higher

initial readiness levels, expect to increase the level by one to three levels, there are some outliers. These outliers are at a very fundamental initial state expecting five (2, both at TRL 2) and even six (1, at TRL 1) levels of maturity increase. On the one hand, one might assume this to be an immense development in the considered time frame, on the other hand, it usually is hard to predict such trajectories the earlier the stage of development. Nevertheless, based on their early state and the predicted increase of maturity, it might be of high interest to start discussion with these high potential low TRL activities, to understand what can be done to support industry involvement this early on, or add actions for additional value for industry.

Figure 15: Distribution of the expected increase in technology readiness level, separated by the initial level.

3.3.2 Possible timescale for new products, processes or services to be market-ready

Figure 16: What would be a possible timescale for the new derived products, processes, or services to be market-ready?

In Figure 16 it is depicted how large the timescale for the newly derived products, processes or services is assumed to be for them to be market ready. This is obviously closely connected to the projection of the state of development that can be achieved within the project phase.

Comparing the answers given previously on the current and prospective technology readiness level with the expected timescale the activities have reported for their R&D activities to reach a market-ready level, one can see a possible underestimation of development time or technological maturity required for a product, process, or service to be fully commercialized. Almost 70% of respondents believe that the new products, processes, and services, generated by R&D activities, will be market ready by the end of I.FAST or slightly after it, relating to a time range from 2 to 5 years from now, while more than half of the activities indicated a technology readiness level of 5 (technology validated in relevant environment or industrially relevant environment) or below.

This corresponds the timetable for “commercial or other use“, as reported prior to the project by some of the tasks. All activities falling under the definition of being relevant for this report (14) have indicated this to be a short to medium-term effort, 35 % of which even state it to be short term. One needs to see, that the commercialization of fundamental R&D projects and bringing them to a market-ready or near market-ready level is not within the traditional scope of scientists at research facilities

like those participating within I.FAST. Therefore, additional industrial views on this might be beneficial to arrive at a consolidated understanding of the necessary time frame and development efforts for optimized exploitation.

3.3.3 Prior contact of the activities with a technology transfer unit/office

Figure 17: Share of activities, that have already had contact to dedicated technology transfer units or technology transfer offices prior to I.FAST in relation to the considered R&D activity.

Activities within the I.FAST project are usually anchored in the respective research facilities of the participating researchers as well. These facilities typically have their own technology transfer units or technology transfer offices, sometimes embedded within for instance administration or strategic management. These offices or units are well-connected in their organization and regularly conduct, e.g., technology screenings to assess innovation and transfer potentials, protect intellectual property, connect with industry, and take care of all surrounding administrative procedures. This is why we are evaluate the connection of activities to technology transfer units not only with questions in this survey, but also in later steps of the work package, identifying the units within I.FAST participating research institutions, facilitating thee access to their services (what is offered by the research institutions and what are the access models), and starting a regular exchange with them for best practices and available programs, especially to support high TRL follow-up activities.

Figure 18: Distributions of activities with contact to technology transfer offices sorted by their current technology readiness level at the beginning of I.FAST (left) and at the end of I.FAST (right).

Looking at the activities, which have answered to our survey, it can be seen that nearly half of them already are in contact with such offices. Mentioned technology transfer units or offices are UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) / Science and Technology Facilities Councils’ (STFC) Business and Innovation Department, the Technology Transfer Office of CIEMAT, CNRS’ valorisation unit, Ecole Polytechnique, as well as the Technology Transfer of INFN.

Considering the maturity level of the activities in this context, Figure 18 shows a rather clear picture. It shows for each group of activities with a certain technology readiness level, which part of them is already in contact to a technology transfer unit, both for the start and end of I.FAST. It is clearly visible that with increasing level also closer contact to transfer offices is seen. Considering those activities that see a rapid development towards a system prototype in operational environment, it is surprising that so far only around 35% have already taken up contact, even though such a development would require close consulting and strong support by such experts.

Figure 19: Comparison of share of activities with same innovation potential that have contact with technology transfer offices. The options denote different types of innovation outcome, with:
 Option 1: The activity will produce innovation in certain scientific applications, but the spill over to industrial partners is expected to be limited (e.g.: industry is expected to supply only off-the-shelf or build-to-print components).
 Option 2: The activity is primarily aimed at applications for science, but industry involvement and associated knowledge transfer can bring significant innovation to industrial products and/or processes.
 Option 3: The activity shows a clear path toward industrial applications, so industrial innovation is definitely an expected outcome.

In the first part of the questionnaire, it was asked what kind of innovation is expected to be generated by the R&D activity. This is revisited in Figure 19, where the three options (limited spill-over to industry, possible innovation, and definitive industrial innovation) are listed, and it is investigated whether the considered innovation potential has an influence on the prior contacting. It can be seen, that especially in the tasks where industrial innovation is a possible but not fully determined outcome, TT offices are more often than not included in support of this process. Also, as is not surprising, in those cases where the innovation potential and spill-over to industrial partners is anyhow expected to be limited, more activities see a lower need to contact such unit.

3.3.4 Perspective of paths leading to industrial exploitation

Figure 20: Share of activities that see a path leading to industrial exploitation at the time of the survey.

Industrial exploitation can be an important part of the innovation process. The number of activities that already see a path towards this is very similar to the number of those that don't. Within the survey, it was assessed what the researchers assume are necessary steps for this to happen. Three types of answers were given:

- Licensing to industry and commercialization,
- R&D in the hands of the industrial partners / partnership,
- Verification & Testing
- Decisions of research institutes to use the developed technology / application of technologies in research projects, and
- Further funding for additional R&D and follow-ups

Especially the first point concerning licensing requires close interaction and support with technology transfer units from an early stage on.

In addition, the proposal presents some exploitation routes of the foreground, e.g.:

- Advertisements at scientific conferences and industrial events
- Seeking partnership with a commercial company

- Support by industrial partners to derive an industrial product/technology (industrialization, commercialization)
- Proof of benefits, verification, testing
- Application at successful projects

Both results from the survey and proposal fit well and cover the same general categories giving indications towards possible further steps to improve the innovation and transfer outcome during the project and beyond.

3.3.5 Beneficial support by dedicated technology transfer units for further industrial exploitation and transfer

An important goal of the analysis is to understand not only where business opportunities lie, but also how to support the R&D activities in fostering these. Therefore, it was asked what type of support is considered most helpful for an increased exploitation potential. In Figure 21, the answers are listed, sorted by their significance. The activities could give multiple answers. What is interesting are especially the top three categories. Support with contacting and searching for companies, e.g., to partner up with, is easy to understand and fits well to the earlier results and could in a later stage possibly be matched with the activities in WP3.3. The top two answers were so far not within the scope of the survey nor within the activities of WP3.

The assessment of commercial potentials is considered rather useful in this context, which is most probably due to the fact, that typical scientific R&D efforts based within research institutions usually do not consider the commercial potentials of their work in advance. This is clear, as they do not require any sort of business plan consideration before addressing the research topic but have other motives. As a result, there is not experience or expertise in such assessments, while the topics considered in I.FAST mostly are in addition extremely challenging in this respect. Nevertheless, for instance to optimize industrial value or to foster the facilitation of start-ups this is a beneficial prerequisite, as it allows for understanding possible routes of exploitation and also supports the definition of follow-up activities with commercialization relevance.

What was also deemed helpful for this cause is consulting regarding IP and licensing matters. Also, in this regard, while necessary to consider for optimal commercialization and technology transfer, this is usually outside the direct scope of the researchers and at the same time a complex matter, especially in international environments and in projects with many participants.

Figure 21: Beneficial support by technology transfer units.

Therefore, for instance in LEAPS-INNOV, there are dedicated intellectual-property rights webinars, intended to support the teams in dealing with the complex issues of intellectual property in the context of valorizing R&D results and in working with industry.

This general result corresponds well with Figure 23, where it can clearly be seen that less than half of the activities are at the time of the survey planning to act to protect the IP that is produced in the task. While considering the early stage of most of the developments, this is not very surprising, taking into account the expected degree of novelty in many tasks, one could imagine a much larger percentage.

Comparing the answers individual activities gave regarding the aspects shown in Figure 21 and Figure 23, it can be found that there is no obvious relationship between planned IP protection and answering that support in these matters would be beneficial (see Figure 22).

Figure 22: Comparison between IP protection plans and request for support.

We also asked the activities, whether they are aware of any constraints or issues, (e.g., patents, background technology knowledge, publications, etc.) being relevant to the current activities, possibly hindering exploitation. While there are in more than half of the cases (55%) other groups working on the same or similar topic (as can be seen in Figure 24), all answers state they are not aware of any constraints or issues, (e.g., patents, background technology knowledge, publications, etc.) being relevant to the current activities, possibly hindering exploitation.

Figure 23: Percentage of activities currently planning to act to protect the intellectual property produced within the research and development activity.

Figure 24: Is the activity aware of other groups working on the same or a similar topic?

Differences stated compared to these same or similar activities are mostly different technology approaches (5 activities, most answers), but also the choice of materials, final applications, or the expected performance.

3.4 PART 4: QUESTIONS ABOUT APPLICATIONS AND COMMERCIALIZATION

In this last part of the results, it was assessed, whether the activities see applications outside the direct scope of the activity, both with a list of given fields (multiple choice) and free text options. Many aspects that could also belong here were already covered in earlier parts of the report, while other aspects did not yield conclusive or meaningful results. Therefore, only a small part of this field of interest is represented in the following results.

Figure 25: Range of applications seen in other fields.

The activities were asked whether they see application fields outside the direct scope of the activity. The range of applications outside the direct scope is a good indicator of additional commercialization and exploitation potential, as the developments can spill over to other industrial sectors and one can more easily attract new industrial interest from possibly not yet involved partners.

As was already expected beforehand and is rather typical for the considered technologies, the typical fields mentioned are next to accelerator-based technologies for non-scientific applications the area of laser-based technologies as well as medical devices and diagnostics. In the following, the results are summarized for the two most selected applications.

3.4.1 Accelerator-based technologies for non-scientific applications

Here, a number of applications were mentioned, that span fields such as security, material sciences, medical technologies and many more. In principle, the answers conclude, many of the technologies could be relevant for any accelerator system - for instance medical linear accelerators (see separate section on medical devices and connected applications).

Material analysis, for instance for non-destructive testing of materials and devices, e.g., in security contexts such as controls at borders are mentioned for multiple activities as clear additional application. Connected to this, also the topic of X-ray generation with compact Compton sources and MeV-electron diffraction microscopes as a non-scientific application mentioned for another activity plays into this field.

Some activities have a clear path towards such an application as the focus of the activity. One example is a task, which is among other topics working on the development of assumptions for industrial electron accelerator-based sludge processing unit construction and the basic engineering of an electron beam municipal sludge processing line based on industrial electron accelerator. Here, scope of biohazards treatment and biomass valorisation is clear as the design of an advanced electron accelerator plant for biohazards treatment is the direct focus of the activity.

3.4.2 Medical devices and diagnostics

Applications in the broader medical are a quite natural domain for developments around the classical accelerator context. Possible applications addressable, that are outside the direct scope of the R&D activity, are seen for medical isotope production, X-ray generation with compact Compton sources, radiotherapy and hadron therapy, or generally cancer treatment.

4 Conclusions – Suggestions and Next Steps

The picture that emerged from the survey confirmed that activities in I.FAST have in general a good innovation potential and that their TRL is expected to grow significantly during the four years of the project.

Already now, three quarters of the responding activities expect to see industrial innovation or at least consider this a realistic scenario. While many answers to more in-depth questions on the innovation potential were rather specific to the exact activity and the number of answers does not always allow for a meaningful statistical analysis, we could get a first look into the type of innovation (for instance within medical technologies or environmental protection applications) that is foreseen and possible hurdles to achieve it, such as the generally high manufacturing costs involved with the innovation. Questions to assess further opportunities to improve the chance or extent of exploitation have yielded additional insights into the activities ideas, which support the I.FAST innovation and knowledge transfer objectives.

The assessment of the current status of industrial involvement has not brought up many surprises but shown that there is a broad participation of industry to many activities. It can be concluded from the results that while the current set of industrial partners is mostly considered adequate, especially an even stronger industrial involvement of the current participants (e.g., in terms of support with prototyping) is seen as beneficial.

Taking a look into the current level of technological maturity, it can be seen that most activities currently see themselves close to fundamental research levels with an average initial TRL of around 2.6, but already foresee a clear path to higher technology readiness levels within the duration of the I.FAST project, moving the expected TRL at the end of the project to around 5.4. At the same time, nearly half the activities see 4-5 years as the possible timescale for new derived products, processes or services to be market-ready, which is a strong outcome expectation of the activities.

While nearly half the activities already are in contact with some technology transfer offices to support with exploitation and technology transfer, which roughly corresponds to the amount of activities that already see a path leading to industrial exploitation, many respondents noted they would like to see further support of technology transfer units/offices in terms of contacting and searching companies, assessing commercial potentials of their activities, and consulting regarding IP and licenses. Especially regarding the last point, a general IPR training for instance offered by experts from one of the participating facilities in I.FAST, specifically addressed at the R&D activities, could support the innovation and knowledge transfer outcome of I.FAST.

This knowledge transfer report serves as a starting point for following steps. Especially for WP 3.2, the subsequent efforts base on the achieved results and gained insights.

Following this milestone, we will continue with a closer discussion with selected I.FAST activities, on the basis of the knowledge transfer report and the received individual answers, as well as given information on the individual activities, e.g., from proposal and other I.FAST resources.

For this, the first step is the identification of suitable activities from within I.FAST. This will be a subset of the contacted activities, as a prerequisite for in-depth interviews and innovation screening is the response to the combined innovation and knowledge transfer survey. This selected subset does not necessarily consist of those activities that have responded to our survey - for subsequent discussions with the activities, we will refer to the full list and possibly also contact tasks that have not yet participated, if deemed interesting and relevant.

The activities will be approached differently based on the technology readiness levels at the beginning and end of I.FAST, as suitable activities for fostering innovation, technology and knowledge transfer also differ severely.

For low TRL activities, the focus is on a longer time-frame development and early actions: What can be done to support industry involvement or add actions for additional value for industry? How can industrial partners be attracted, where no explicit involvement is planned? Especially for the second question, synergies between Tasks 3.2 and 3.3 are well conceivable.

Regarding high TRL activities, more immediate action for increased innovation outcome and knowledge transfer are possible, so the discussion would resolve closer along the lines of what knowledge and technology transfer activities are planned within the activities.

In both cases, the conducted innovation and knowledge transfer study will serve as a good starting point and also highlight suitable candidates for not only follow-up interviews, but also the following investigations for the business case for one I.FAST R&D sector that will be developed until the end of the project, in collaboration with industry.

The insights in terms of the collaboration with technology transfer units will support the beginning discussions with technology transfer units at the different I.FAST beneficiaries, with the goal of a regular exchange regarding best practices and available programs, especially to support high TRL follow-up activities. Based on these exchanges and the obtained insights of the initial analysis, general measures and instruments will be summed up in a check list to be used at research institutes involved in accelerator R&D.

Additionally, especially regarding the innovation outcome analysis, the conducted survey is embedded within a survey plan that was set up for periodically assessing the innovation outcome of R&D activities in I.FAST, both in terms of initial expectations and of actual achievements. Thus, the results obtained within this initial survey will periodically be reviewed, finally resulting in a complete picture of the knowledge and innovation outcome of the various I.FAST R&D activities.

5 Annexes

5.1 QUESTIONS ADDRESSED IN THE SURVEY

5.1.1 Questions Concerning the Potential of Industrial Innovation of I.FAST Activities

The questions of this section aim at gauging the expectations of the Task Leaders considered relevant for the scope of this analysis concerning the potential of their activities to generate industrial innovations/applications. Furthermore, considering that most of the R&D activities with potential industrial application stand at different starting TRL levels and that the project seeks to bring them closer to the market validation phase, this section also sets the stage for the following questions related to the potential for technology transfer activities connected with the declared innovation expectations.

1. Please, report the R&D activity goal of your task.
2. What kind of innovation is it expected to be generated by your R&D activity?
3. What kind of new or improved products, processes or services are expected to be eventually generated from the R&D activity?
4. Do you see any factors that may represent obstacles towards the effective exploitation of the innovation potential by industry?
5. Is there any possibility to strengthen this limited innovation spill-over?
6. What possibilities do you see?
7. What are the opportunities to improve the chance or the extent of this exploitation?
8. What would be a possible timescale for the new derived products, processes, or services to be market-ready?

5.1.2 Questions on the Industrial Participation and Involvement in I.FAST Activities

The innovation potential can in many cases one be fulfilled with a strong and meaningful involvement of involved industrial partners, for instance in terms of support within a common development. Therefore, for this report and the initial assessment of the activities it is crucial to highlight in which ways the various industrial partners are participating, how they are involved, how they are distributed and where there might be leverage for improving impact by stronger or more involvement. Questions aimed at clearing this aspect of the survey are selected in this section.

1. How many companies are currently collaborating in your I.FAST task?
2. Are you planning to take some actions to explore the possibility of an industrial involvement in the R&D activity?
3. How are you going to reach companies that can be potential collaborators?
4. Do you need some help in finding and contacting them?
5. How much do you think that enlarging the set of companies currently engaged could benefit your R&D activities?
6. What kind of companies would you like to participate/what should these companies bring with them?
7. Do you need help with the search of additional companies?
8. How much can your activities benefit by stronger involvement of the companies currently engaged?
9. What form of additional industrial involvement of the companies currently engaged would be beneficial?

5.1.3 Questions About Technology Transfer Expectations

The exploitation of the fore- and background of the tasks within I.FAST depends on several aspects. The following questions are important to assess the value and potential of the work in terms of exploitation as well as possible challenges.

1. At which technology readiness level (TRL) is the activity right now, and where is it projected to be at the end of the project? [Right now]
2. At which technology readiness level (TRL) is the activity right now, and where is it projected to be at the end of the project? [At the end of the project]
3. Do you already see a path that leads to industrial exploitation or commercialization?
4. What are necessary additional steps for this to happen (e.g., after the I.FAST project is over)?
5. Are parts of the developments carried out also in contexts outside I.FAST?
6. Are you aware of other groups working on the same or a similar topic?
7. Where are possible differences?
8. Are you aware of any constraints or issues, (e.g., patents, background technology knowledge, publications, etc.) being relevant to the current activities, possibly hindering exploitation?
9. If yes, which problems do you see?
10. Is there any software to be developed within the research activity?
11. How is the software developed?
12. Is the source code shared within the partners of the activity?
13. Have you planned to take actions to protect the IP produced in the R&D activity?

14. Is support needed?
15. How is the licensing planned?
16. Are you already in contact with a TT office? Which one?
17. What support by dedicated technology transfer units would be beneficial for further industrial exploitation

5.1.4 Questions About Applications and Commercialization

Finally, it was assessed whether the activities see applications outside the direct scope of the activity, both with a list of given fields (multiple choice) and free text options.

1. Do you see application fields outside the direct scope of the activity, e.g., in other industrial sectors?

5.2 FLOWCHARTS OF THE SURVEY STRUCTURE AND QUESTIONS

To allow readers a better understanding of the overall structure of the survey and the relationships between the different questions it is made of, we represented the whole questionnaire section by section in the graphic flowchart below. For the sake of readability, we have not repeated the questions’ texts inside the frames of the chart but only the reference to their number which follows the numeration described above.

In the chart, questions will be coloured in blue, while multiple choice answers are represented in orange, questions soliciting free texts feedbacks stand after all the other questions where orange squares are not present.

5.2.1 1st Part of the Survey - questions concerning the potential of industrial innovation of i.fast activities

5.2.2 2nd Part of the Survey - questions on the industrial participation and involvement in i.fast activities

5.2.3 3rd Part of the survey - questions about technology transfer expectations

5.2.4 4th Part of the Survey - question about applications and commercialization

5.3 LIST OF ACTIVITIES CONSIDERED RELEVANT FOR THE SURVEY AND ANALYSIS

The following list Table 1 shows the relevant activities addressed within the conducted survey and subsequent analysis. It is based on the definition of relevant activities for this survey and analysis as it is explained in Section 1.4. All these tasks have received the questionnaire, but not all have responded within the given time frame until this milestone report. Nevertheless, for subsequent discussions with the activities, we will refer to this list and possibly also contact tasks that have not yet participated.

Table 1: Tasks identified as relevant for the scope of this survey.

Task	Task Description	Involved Companies (Participants)
4.3	Innovative beam windows for high-power accelerator applications	RHP Technology (Austria)
4.4	Large scale Carbide-Carbon Materials for multipurpose applications	Nanoker Research SL (Spain)
5.3	Improvement of Resonant slow EXtraction spill quality (REX)	Bergoz Instrumentation (France), Barthel HF-Technik GmbH (Germany)
6.2	Lasers for Plasma Acceleration (LASPLA)	Thales AVS France SAS (France), Amplitude Systemes (France), Thales ALS France (France)
6.3	Multi-scale Innovative targets for laser-plasma accelerators	None
6.4	Laser focal Spot Stabilization Systems (L3S)	Amplitude Systemes (France), Thales ALS France (France)
7.2	Enabling technologies for ultra-low emittance rings	None
7.3	Variable Dipole for the upgrade of the ELETTRA storage ring	KYMA S.R.L. (Italy)
7.4	Very high gradient RF Guns operating in the C-band RF technology	KYMA S.R.L. (Italy), Comeb s.r.l. (Italy), VDL Enabling Technologies Group Precision (Netherlands)
7.5	CompactLight Prototype Accelerating Structures	Comeb s.r.l. (Italy), VDL Enabling Technologies Group Precision (Netherlands), TMD Technologies Limited (UK)
8.2	Preliminary Engineering design of curved Canted Cosine Theta (CCT) magnet	None
8.3	Preliminary Engineering design of HTS CCT	None

8.4	Construction of curved CCT magnet demonstrator	Scanditronix Magnet AB (Sweden), Bilfinger Moell GmbH (Germany)
8.5	Construction of the HTS CCT magnet demonstrator	Bilfinger Moell GmbH (Germany), Elytt Energy SL (Spain)
8.6	Development of ReBCO HTS Nuclotron cable	None
9.2	Innovative Superconducting (SC) Accelerating Cavity Prototype	Piccoli S.R.L. (Italy)
9.3	Optimisation of process parameters and target development for SRF cavity coating with A15 material	None
9.4	Surface engineering by Atomic Layer Deposition (ALD)	None
9.5	Improvement of mechanical and superconducting properties of RF resonator by laser radiation	None
9.6	Optimization of flat SRF thin films production procedure	None
10.4	Development of AM-manufactured superconductive RF cavities	None
10.5	Photon Stimulated Desorption (PSD) from NEG coatings for accelerator vacuum chambers	None
10.7	Development of electro-optical waveguide sensors as beam electric field sensors	None
11.2	High Efficiency Klystron Industrial Prototype	Thales AVS France SAS (France)
11.3	Permanent Magnet Quadrupoles & Combined Function Magnets for Ultra Low-Emittance Rings	Kyma SRL (Italy)
12.2	Design of advanced electron accelerator plant for biohazards treatment	None
12.3	Design of Internal RF Ion Source for Cyclotrons	General Electrics (GEMS PET Systems AB) (Sweden), Cyclomed Technologies SL (Spain)
13.3	New RF amplifiers based on GaN semiconductors	None

5.4 TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL DEFINITIONS

The so-called Technology Readiness Level is an estimate for the maturity level of a technology during the research and development process, originally coined in aerospace technology. It was used there to describe the degree of development of a technical product. Within the frame of Horizon 2020 (European Commission, 2014), the TRL definition was adapted in the annex of the work program. It ranges on the scale from TRL 1 to TRL 9.

Table 2: Definition of Technology Readiness Levels.

<i>TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL</i>	<i>DEFINITION – EUROPEAN UNION</i>
TRL 1	Basic principles observed
TRL 2	Technology concept formulated
TRL 3	Experimental proof of concept
TRL 4	Technology validated in lab
TRL 5	Technology validated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
TRL 6	Technology demonstrated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
TRL 7	System prototype demonstration in operational environment
TRL 8	System complete and qualified
TRL 9	Actual system proven in operational environment (competitive manufacturing in the case of key enabling technologies; or in space)

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8 Glossary

Acronym	Definition
KT	Knowledge Transfer
TT	Technology Transfer
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package

9 Industry Engagement Tasks Formulation

Task 3.1: Coordination and industrial partnership support (INFN, DESY, CIEMAT, CERN, CEA)

An Industry Advisory Board (IAB), composed of representatives from companies working in the most relevant accelerator industrial sectors, from Big Science national industry associations, and from the European ILO and TT organizations, will be setup within three months from the start of the project. The IAB will advise the project management on how to optimize the impact of the industrial participation in improving the competitiveness of European SMEs, to stimulate the applications of R&D results for addressing the most crucial societal challenges, and to remove the obstacles, including communication bottlenecks, which limit the effectiveness of collaboration with Research and Technology Infrastructures. The IAB could also contribute to the selection of proposals for training secondments in task WP2.4 and in the organisation of the Innovation Fund programme.

To support the companies involved in I.FAST, a few actions will be carried out within the first six months:

- A compendium illustrating the structure of the project and how the interaction with industry is organized will be distributed to companies engaged in I.FAST. It will, in particular, emphasize the general principles adopted for the management of the IP originated in the I.FAST activities.
- A dedicated contact channel will be established to collect suggestions from the collaborating companies on possible ways of improving the effectiveness and the impact of their participation in I.FAST.
- A survey plan will be setup for periodically assessing the innovation outcome of R&D activities in I.FAST, both in terms of initial expectations and of actual achievements.

A mid-term workshop will be organized, to evaluate the progress achieved in pursuing I.FAST innovation goals, to discuss how to address possible difficulties and shortcomings, and to present an up-to-date outlook of the perspectives of industrial involvement in accelerator developments and of the related business opportunities. The workshop will represent an initiative for communicating and promoting the outcome of the industrial contributions in I.FAST activities to the main stake holders and will be part of the outreach strategy defined in collaboration with WP2. All these Technology Transfer actions will be executed in a coordinated manner by the Knowledge Transfer offices of DESY, CERN and CIEMAT.

Task 3.1: Coordination and industrial partnership support M1 – M48

- Setup and organize the work of the I.FAST Industry Advisory Board (IAB).
- Support the companies participating in I.FAST.
- Organize the I.FAST industrial workshop.

D3.1: Industry Workshop Report (Report to document the outcome of the workshop - M26)

MS8: Industry Advisory Board launch (M6)

Task 3.2: Knowledge Transfer and Business opportunities in accelerator R&D (DESY, UKRI, CERN)

Each R&D activity in I.FAST will be asked to characterize the KT between RI and industry expected to be produced, and what actions are planned for extracting the best added value for the European industry competitiveness. Activities at low TRL without an explicit involvement of private companies will be invited to discuss actions to attract industrial partners. The outcome of these initial actions will be summarized in a report describing the I.FAST KT objectives. Contacts with the TT offices of the I.FAST participating Research Institutions will then be established to facilitate the access to services provided by them and by other local KT facilitators, like innovation centres and incubators, as well as to inform the I.FAST partners about best practices and programs that might be available, in particular at regional level, dedicated to support possible high TRL follow up activities.

The business case for one I.FAST R&D sector will be developed, in collaboration with industry, and the outcome made available. General measures and instruments will be summed up in a check list to be used at research institutes involved in accelerator R&D. The collected information will be presented and discussed in a session of the I.FAST Industry Workshop.

Task 3.2: Knowledge Transfer and Business opportunities in accelerator R&D M1 – M48

- Foster KT to industry and stimulate the build-up of added industrial value in terms of creating new IP, establishing new activities for existing companies, and facilitating the creation of spin-offs.
- Support the beneficiaries in achieving an optimal exploitation of the KT originated by I.FAST.

D3.2: Business development case report (Description of the activities carried out and of the results obtained - M36)

MS9: I.FAST KT Report ready (M10)

Task 3.3: Extended participation of industry in collaborative R&D activities (CIEMAT, CERN, CEA)

An issue that frequently emerged in the feedback provided by companies participating in previous projects concerns the perceived unexploited potential contribution that industry could provide in R&D activities if engaged earlier in the process and if asked to contribute in a more organic way with their specific technical and managerial competences. This could bring significant benefits in terms of design choices that may lead to faster, cheaper, and more robust products with a benefit for the companies themselves. This approach requires early common strategies between research labs and industry in order to define key aspects, such as, among others, IPR management, clear cost-added value definition for avoiding possible drawbacks related to additional initial costs, risk of reduced competition, loss of key technical knowledge, etc.

To address this issue, a detailed working plan will be agreed upon and then executed, in collaboration with the industry association INDUCIENCIA and the industrial innovation support organization CDTI. The initial action in the plan will consist of performing a survey among the companies to indicate and characterize possible ways of extending the industrial contributions to the R&D activities. Successively, feedback will be collected from RIs and TIs on the conditions that should be fulfilled to make the extended contributions possible. Finally, the material received will be analyzed and discussed, and a final report will be prepared with a set of guidelines for the RIs.

Task 3.3: Extended participation of industry in collaborative R&D activities M1 – M48

- Address the requests by industry for an extended participation in R&D activities through early engagement in low TRL developments and more effective exploitation of specific capabilities owned by private companies.
- Define the conditions and the obstacles to be overcome for achieving such goals.

D3.3: Report on extended industrial contributions in R&D activities (Guidelines to improve the participation of private companies in R&D activities - M36)

M10: Collection of feedback from industrial partners and RIs participating in IFAST (M20)